

Issue/problem

The US Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) recently [announced](#) that it would gradually phase out funding for mRNA vaccine development.

Description of the problem

HHS Secretary, Robert F. Kennedy Jr., announced that nearly US\$500 million will be cut from the Biomedical Advanced Research and Development Authority (BARDA)'s budget. Contracts with [Emory University](#) and [Tiba Biotech](#) will be ended, while mRNA-related work by [Luminary Labs](#), [ModeX](#), and [Seqirus](#) will be descope. Proposals from Pfizer, Sanofi Pasteur, and Gritstone will also be rejected. Projects already in late-stage development will be allowed to continue. In all, 22 projects will be affected.

Kennedy Jr. attempted to justify these cuts by false claims that mRNA vaccines fail to adequately protect against influenza and COVID. The administration has promised further investment in “better solutions.”

Results

BARDA's [mandate](#) includes pandemic preparedness, with rapid vaccine development being a [key element](#) to slow the spread of outbreaks. The [role](#) mRNA vaccines played in slowing the recent COVID-19 pandemic highlights the importance of vaccine development pipelines. Cutting funding for mRNA vaccine programs—particularly those targeting influenza and coronavirus immunity—threatens to weaken a core component of the agency's mission and slow pandemic response worldwide.

Moreover, mRNA technology has the potential to create low-cost preventative therapies or treatments for a [wide range](#) of [pathologies](#), including rare diseases. These therapies offer [could open](#) pathways for prevention and treatment but cutting funding to development in this area risks undermining future breakthroughs.

Lessons learned

This funding cut is situated in a [larger movement](#) of the US federal government retreating from science funding, prompting a [large number](#) of scientists to consider leaving the country. Together, these trends give an opportunity for other countries to step in and fill the gap caused by the US government's exit from science funding, possibly allowing them to become leaders in innovation. To that effect, [Australia](#) and the [EU](#) have recently launched initiatives to recruit American scientists.